

MECHANICAL AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATIONS OF PAN-DERIVED HOLLOW CARBON NANOFIBERS

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Keywords: *co-axial electrospinning, hollow carbon nanofiber, nano-tensile test, turbostratic microstructure*

1 Introduction

Carbon nanofibers (CNFs) have been widely researched due to their potential applications to multifunctional composites. Continuous CNFs have been manufactured by electrospinning and subsequent carbonization of precursor polymers because those CNFs may be ideal for strengthening, stiffening and toughening of polymer matrix compared to vapour grown CNFs.

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) has been commonly used as a precursor for CNFs because it has good electrospinnability and its successful conversion to carbonaceous structure can be simply done by thermal treatment. Early study reported relatively lower mechanical properties (bending modulus 63 GPa and fracture stress 0.64 GPa) of individual PAN-derived CNFs carbonized at 1100°C [1]. High tensile strength and elastic modulus (3.5 and 172 GPa) were reported for CNFs carbonized at 1400°C, while some CNFs showed 2% ultimate strain and strengths over 4.5 GPa [2]. On the other hand, hollow CNFs (HCNFs) have been manufactured using co-axial electrospinning to develop multifunctional materials via the incorporation of nanoparticles into the core or to utilize larger surface area than solid CNFs. Some applications of HCNFs were suggested, including fluidic delivery and metal core-carbon shell composite for Li-ion battery anodic applications [3, 4]. Even though the mechanical properties are the fundamental element to explore their applications, the tensile strength and modulus of HCNFs have not been researched yet.

This study was aimed to measure the tensile strength and elastic modulus of HCNFs [5], and to investigate the effect of turbostratic carbon structure

in HCNFs on their strength according to the manufacturing conditions.

2 Experimental

2.1 Hollow CNFs preparation

Styrene-acrylonitrile (SAN) and PAN were used to manufacture HCNF. Here SAN ($M_w = 120,000$ g/mol, Acrylonitrile 28.5 mol%) was used as a sacrificial core, while PAN ($M_w = 200,000$ g/mol) remained as the shell component after carbonization. Both were resolved into *N, N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF, purity: 99.5%) with the specific concentration (e.g., PAN 10 and 20 wt% and SAN 30 wt%). Two PAN concentrations were selected to investigate the effect of the wall thickness on the tensile properties of HCNFs. Detailed conditions for co-axial electrospinning process and subsequent carbonization can be found elsewhere [5]. The SAN core/PAN shell nanofibers were treated in a continuous thermal process for the stabilization and carbonization. In the stabilization process, PAN experienced the dehydrogenation and cyclization by chemical reaction with oxygen in air atmosphere, while SAN melt. In the subsequent carbonization, stabilized PAN transformed to short-range-ordered graphitic structure, while SAN was thermally decomposed into gaseous phases, resulting in HCNFs as shown schematically in Fig.1.

2.2 Micro-structural characterizations

Spectroscopic characterizations were employed to investigate the microstructure and chemical bonding of coaxially spun nanofibers and carbonization HCNF. Firstly, FT-IR analysis was conducted to

observe the micro-structural change of the SAN core/PAN shell nanofibers during the stabilization and carbonization process. Raman spectroscopy and wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) were also carried out to evaluate the carbonized structures of HCNFs. Their tubular structures and morphologies were investigated by both field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) and transmission electron microscope (TEM). In addition, the precise microstructure of HCNFs was characterized with high resolution transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM).

2.3 Nano-tensile test

Focused ion beam (FIB) was used to cut and attach single HCNF to a testing device. The one end of the HCNF was especially loaded on a nanomanipulator (Kleindiek, MM3A), while the other end was attached to an AFM cantilever (see Fig. 2). The HCNF was glued by Pt deposition within FIB. The tensile test was then carried out by displacing the manipulator. The force was calculated using a piezoelectric sensor and the deformation of the cantilever.

Fig. 1. Preparation of HCNFs

Fig. 2. Sampling of single HCNF for nano-tensile test.

3 Results and discussion

HCNFs prepared in this study were shown in Fig. 3. Our previous study showed that the hollowness of SAN core/PAN shell nanofiber-derived HCNFs could be readily controlled by varying the solution concentration and flow rate. The diameter of HCNTs was affected by both core and shell parameters, while their wall thickness was mainly determined by the shell concentration. Moreover, the microstructure of HCNFs was investigated for two HCNFs with different wall thickness. The thinner (Fig. 3(a) PAN 10 wt% and SAN 30 wt%) and thicker hollow CNF (Fig.3 (b) PAN 20 wt% and SAN 30 wt%) were chosen to establish a relationship between their microstructure and mechanical properties.

Fig. 3. HCNFs with different wall thickness and size prepared by varying shell concentrations: (a) 10 wt% and (b) 20 wt%, respectively.

The carbonized structure was evaluated by WAXD analysis in Fig. 4. It showed the three equatorial peaks: primary (002), secondary (10 l) and tertiary (004) planes of the carbon graphitic layers. The d -

spacing value of (002) planes ($2\theta = 24.3^\circ$) were calculated to be 0.366 nm, which is larger than that of graphite (0.335 nm), implying that the microstructure of HCNFs is a turbostratic carbon structure with a slightly mismatched layer-sequence.

Fig. 4. WAXD curves of hollow CNFs.

The crystallites of the thinner HCNFs were poorly developed than the thicker HCNFs as shown in Fig. 5, even though the crystallinity of the former (42.7%) was higher than that of the latter HCNFs (36.2%). Both the crystallite size (L_a) and thickness (L_c) of the thinner HCNFs were significantly less than those of the thicker HCNFs (see reciprocal lattices in Fig. 5 for comparison).

Fig. 5. HR-TEM images and reciprocal lattices of selected HCNFs: (a) thinner and (b) thicker samples.

Fig. 6. (a) The thinner HCNFs mounted between nanomanipulator and AFM cantilever. (b) Its engineering stress-strain curve.

Fig. 6 shows the stress-strain curve of the thinner HCNFs. As the elastic modulus and tensile strength were 15.9 GPa and 0.5 GPa, respectively, and the ultimate strain was 3.13%, they were much lower than reported values for solid CNF, while the ultimate strain was higher than reported values [1, 2], even though the direct comparison was not possible due to different macroscopic structure, i.e., hollow and solid CNFs. The low strength was probably ascribed to less developed microstructure (crystallites) and their random orientation in the thinner HCNFs. On the other hand, the thicker CNFs showed higher elastic modulus and strength (60 GPa and 1.2 GPa) than the thinner HCNFs. These results demonstrate that the microstructure of HCNFs, in

particular crystal size and orientation, is extremely important factor to determine their mechanical properties.

Next the fractured surfaces of the HCNFs were investigated using HR-TEM (Fig. 7). It is clear that the fracture occurred in the transverse direction to the graphitic layers for both HCNFs. This can be explained by the bonding forces of carbons. In the turbostratic carbon crystallites, carbon atoms in the graphitic layers are covalently bonded by sp^2 hybridization, while each graphitic layer is bonded by van der Waals force. On the other hand, carbon atoms in the amorphous region are covalently bonded with sp^3 hybrid structure. The bonding strengths of these bonds were reported to be 350 and 430 kJ/mol for sp^3 and sp^2 hybrid bondings, respectively [6]. Note that van der Waals bonding between the graphitic layer is very small (7 kJ/mol) compared to other bonding force [7]. Therefore, graphitic layers are supposed to break firstly for randomly oriented crystals. As shown in Fig. 5, the present HCNFs developed the turbostratic carbon crystallites during the thermal treatment, which were randomly oriented without tension. As a result, the graphitic layers within HCNFs were separated due to their weak bonding, resulting in such low tensile modulus and strength. If tension is provided to HCNFs during the thermal treatment, it may be expected that strong HCNF can be manufactured.

4 Summary

Two HCNFs with different hollowness and wall thicknesses were prepared to evaluate their mechanical properties. The effect of the microstructure on the tensile strength of HCNFs was investigated using a nanotensile test. The elastic modulus and tensile strength of the thinner HCNFs were about 15.9 and 0.5 GPa, whereas 60 and 1.2 GPa for the thicker HCNFs. The fracture surfaces observed by HR-TEM revealed that such low strength were caused by randomly oriented turbostratic carbon structures of the present HCNFs. Further research will be directed to orient the crystallites along the fiber axis and its results will be presented at the conference.

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Fig. 7. The microstructures of both samples at fracture surfaces.